

EFFECTIVENESS OF L-ARGININE IN THE TREATMENT OF ERECTILE DYSFUNCTION WITH LONG-TERM USE

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Abstract. *The aim of the study was to assess the effectiveness of L-arginine (Tivortin® aspartate by "Yuria-Pharm") in erectile dysfunction caused by endothelial dysfunction. The study involved 36 men aged 47 to 58 years, suffering from type 2 diabetes, stage I hypertension, obesity of stage I-II, dyslipidemia, and mild to moderate erectile dysfunction. The patients received intravenous infusions of Arginine hydrochloride (Tivortin® infusion solution) at a dose of 42 mg/ml, 100 ml for 5 days, followed by oral administration of L-Arginine aspartate (Tivortin® aspartate) 10 ml twice a day with meals for 60 days.*

The article presents data indicating the necessity of using L-arginine as monotherapy (Tivortin® aspartate), which has a positive effect on the severity of erections in patients with erectile dysfunction caused by endothelial dysfunction.

Keywords: *mild and moderate erectile dysfunction, penile erection, endothelial dysfunction.*

Relevance. Erectile dysfunction (ED) is a persistent or recurrent inability to achieve or maintain an erection sufficient for sexual intercourse [1,2,3]. ED affects not only the physiological but also the psychological characteristics of a man [2,5]. Consequently, the problem of diagnosing and treating ED has not only medical but also social significance. The term ED is applicable to a wide range of erectile dysfunctions: from partial failure of erection before ejaculation to its complete loss. The “delicacy” of the problem is that not every patient is able to come to the doctor with complaints of erectile dysfunction. Only 3% of men independently consult a urologist with complaints of decreased erectile quality [3,4,6]. At the same time, only 30-40% of doctors find out the state of erectile function in all patients over 40 years old, and 60% of specialists are never interested in the quality of the patient’s sexual life [4,7].

Penile erection is a physiological process of spontaneous or sexually induced enlargement and hardening of the penis as a result of a complex interaction of psychological, nervous, vascular and endocrine factors [1,3,4,7]. The process of relaxation of the smooth muscles of the corpora cavernosa, which is crucial for penile erection, occurs not only due to sympathetic adrenergic inhibition and parasympathetic cholinergic stimulation, but also the production of nitric oxide (NO), which is an important mediator of smooth muscle relaxation [1,8,9].

The prevalence of erectile dysfunction (ED) increases with age and is therefore much higher in older men than in young men. According to the literature, the prevalence of ED is estimated in the range from 1 to 15% in men aged 30-50 years, from 6 to 40% in men aged 50-80 years, and in men over 70 years, the prevalence of ED is observed from 50 to 100% [2,10].

One of the possible ways to eliminate endothelial dysfunction is to enhance the synthesis of NO from L-arginine. The latter is the main substrate for the synthesis of NO [3,4,10].

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of L-arginine (Tivortin® aspartate by Yuria-Pharm) in ED caused by endothelial dysfunction.

Materials and methods. The study included 36 men aged 47-58 years suffering from type II diabetes mellitus, hypertension (stage I), obesity stages I-II, dyslipidemia, mild to moderate ED. Patients received intravenous infusions of Arginine hydrochloride (Tivortin® infusion solution) at a dosage of 42 mg/ml, 100 ml for 5 days, then took orally L-Arginine aspartate (Tivortin® aspartate) 10 ml 2 times a day during meals for 60 days. Statistical processing of the obtained data and analysis of the study results were performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics V.21 computer program.

Results of the study. The parameters characterizing the quality of erections in patients with ED before and after treatment are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Assessment of the quality of erections

Quality of erection	Before treatment, n=36 n=36n=36, n=36	After treatment, n=36, n=36
Lack of erection	18 (50%)	0 (0%)
Tumescence without rigidity	12 (33,3%)	16 (44,4%)
Partial erection	7(19,4%)	17 (47,2%)*
Full erection	0 (0%)	8 (22,2%)

Note: n is the number of patients, * - $p < 0.05$

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, the vast majority (30 people - 83.3%) of patients with ED were unable to perform sexual intercourse before treatment due to insufficient erection. After treatment, 25 (69.4%) patients were able to perform intimate intercourse with sufficient erection, while in 8 (22.2%) patients, erection was fully restored.

The dynamics of the International Index of Erectile Function (IIEF) scale indicators are presented in Table. 2.

Table 2

IIEF scale indicators

Indicator	Before treatment (M±m)	After treatment M±m)
Achieving an erection (IIEF-1)	1,9±0,1	3,9±0,3*
Erection with sexual stimulation (IIEF -2)	2,2±0,15	$p > 0,05$
Sufficiency of erection (IIEF-3)	2,3±0,2	4,1±0,2*
Maintaining erection (IIEF-4)	2,2±0,1	4,0±0,3*
Erection before completion of sexual intercourse (IIEF-5)	2,7±0,3	4,2±0,1*
Number of attempts to have sexual intercourse (IIEF-6)	2,4±0,2	4,0±0,15*
Satisfaction with sexual intercourse (IIEF-7)	2,1±1,1	4,6±0,2*
Pleasure from sexual intercourse (IIEF-8)	1,8±0,15	4,3±0,2*
Frequency of ejaculations (IIEF-9)	2,1±0,2	2,8±0,3*
Frequency of orgasms (IIEF-10)	2,4±0,1	2,9±0,15
Sexual desire (IIEF-11)	3,4±0,2	4,2±0,3*
Sexual desire (frequency) (IIEF-12)	3,7±0,3	3,9±0,2

Satisfaction with sexual life (IIEF-13)	1,4±0,15	3,6±0,1*
Satisfaction with sexual life with partner (IIEF-14)	2,0±0,1	3,9±0,2*
Confidence in achieving and maintaining an erection (IIEF-15)	2,1±0,2	4,8±0,3*

Note: *-p<0.05

As can be seen from the data in Table 2, the parameters characterizing the quality of erections after taking L-Arginine aspartate (IIEF 1,2,3,4,5,15) improved sufficiently, which allowed patients to increase sexual activity (IIEF-6). As a result of satisfaction with sexual intercourse (IIEF-7), sexual desire increased (IIEF-11) and overall satisfaction with sexual life increased (IIEF-14).

Hemodynamic parameters in the penis are presented in Table. 3.

Table 3

Penile vessel Doppler sonography parameters

Parameter	Before treatment (M±m)	After treatment (M±m)
Peak systolic velocity, cm/s	16,5±0,9	28,3±0,4*
End diastolic velocity, cm/s	3,7±1,0	2,8±0,7

Note: *-p<0.05

According to the penile vessel Doppler sonography parameters, after a course of L-Arginine aspartate, blood flow to the cavernous bodies significantly increased, while the end diastolic velocity did not change.

Conclusions. Thus, the use of L-arginine as monotherapy (Tivortin® aspartate) has a positive effect on the severity of erections in patients with ED caused by endothelial dysfunction. This is confirmed by both the subjective assessment of patients and the data of the IIEF questionnaire and Doppler ultrasound parameters characterizing the improvement of blood flow in the penis. L-arginine can be recommended as a drug for pathogenetic therapy in ED of vascular genesis.

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